

1. GM population and rainfall pattern at Goa, India, 1981.

GM infestation and grain yield of different plantings, Goa, India,^a 1981.

Planting date	Silvershoot (%)						Grain yield (t/ha)	
	30 DT		45 DT		75 DT		1980	1981
	1980	1981	1980	1981	1980	1981		
7 Jun	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a	6.9 a	5.1 a
22 Jun	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a	15 b	6.2 a	4.7 b
7 Jul	0 a	3 b	6 b	30 b	23 c	20 c	4.7 b	3.2 c
22 Jul	6 b	23 c	15 c	32 b	11 b	29 d	4.2 b	1.6 d

^a Separation of means in a column at 5 % level.

2. Relation between GM infestation and grain yield at Goa, India, 1981.

and at harvest. Rainfall and daily light trap catches of GM were recorded from Jun to Oct 1981 (Fig. 1).

The early planted crop had no GM damage up to 45 DT, and GM infestation later had minimal impact on grain yield. GM attacked late-planted crops at 30 DT and significantly reduced yield (see table). GM infestation at 30 DT in 1981 was significantly and negatively correlated with grain yield ($r = -0.694$) (Fig. 2).

Peak GM population was in Sep. about 2 mo after peak rainfall, which may indicate probable GM outbreak. Therefore, rice planted early (Jun) in the monsoon has better chance of escaping infestation than late crops.

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Oviposition of rice whorl maggot (RWM) in wet seedbeds

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RWM *Hydrellia philippina* Ferino is a major pest of irrigated rice in central Luzon, Philippines. Farmers often spray their wet seedbeds several times, even a few days before pulling the seedlings (20-25 d after seeding [DAS]). Late

spraying may kill RWM eggs laid in the seedbed before transplanting. Perhaps RWM control by foliar sprays after transplanting is inadequate because of seedbed infestation.

RWM eggs were monitored at 3d intervals from 7 to 24 DAS on 50 randomly selected plants 0, 10, 20, 30, 100, 130, 150 cm from the edges of 7 farmers' seedbeds. Wooden planks were set over the seedbeds so plants could be

removed without disturbing the rest of the seedbed.

Most eggs were laid on the edges of seedbeds (Fig. 1), which indicates that RWM is attracted to the open standing water around seedbeds (Fig. 2a) but will lay a few eggs in the closed canopies of seedbeds, on direct-seeded lowland rice, or on plants growing over azolla.

Central Luzon farmers leave the deep-rooted seedlings along the edges of

1. RWM egg distribution sampled from 9 flooded, wet seedbeds, Zaragoza, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1984.

seedbeds (Fig. 2b), and therefore carry insignificant numbers of RWM eggs to the field. Most infestation, therefore, begins after transplanting.

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2a. Wet seedbeds showing standing water between adjacent beds.

2b. Wet seedbeds after seedlings are pulled, leaving the borders.

Pest Control and Management DISEASES

Spread of rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) in Bicol, Philippines

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Tungro (RTV) is a disease complex associated with rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and RTSV. Previous

studies showed that susceptible varieties with RTV symptoms were generally infected with both RTBV and RTSV and that those without symptoms often were infected only with RTSV.

To confirm the occurrence of RTSV and identify vector species, *Nephotettix virescens*, *N. nigropictus*, and *Recilia dorsalis* were collected from rice fields in Bicol, Philippines, in Feb and Mar 1985.

Vector populations were high, but RTV incidence was low or nonexistent. The vectors were allowed overnight inoculation access on TN1 seedlings in test tubes. All inoculated seedlings were tested in ELISA for RTBV and RTSV 14–21 d after inoculation.

In about 32 ha of rice fields in 7 municipalities, leaf samples were collected from some rice plants with